

Scelotes mirus

Montane Burrowing Skink

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© L. Kemp

Group: Reptile

Size: 10-20 cm (total body length)

Distribution:

Near-endemic to South Africa, occurring in South Africa (Mpumalanga, extending south to northern KwaZulu-Natal) and Eswatini.

Importance:

It serves as an important model species in specific limb development stage in *Scelotes* genus (full limb digit development stage, with forelimb digit = 5, hindlimb digit number = 5) to study genomic evolution of vertebrates. It has a restricted distribution, occurring in distinct habitats and regions, making them excellent model species for biogeographic and molecular ecology studies.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 24.25 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 3.63 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 1.5 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 91.4% [Single: 88.2%, Duplicated: 3.1%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 185.25 kilobases

Contig number: 25 296

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